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Psychological Determinants of Sports Participation and Engagement of College Students: Basis for a Development Program

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Abstract

This study examines the psychological determinants of sports participation and engagement of college students enrolled in undergraduate program for the academic year 2024-2025. This study was conducted on the 3rd week of October 2024 at colleges and universities in Cotabato Province. The goal of this correlational study was to determine the relationship between the psychological determinants of sports participation and sports engagement of college students at selected state universities and colleges within Cotabato Province. The study had a total of 400 respondents from different colleges and universities. Moreover, two adapted research instruments were used to determine the relationship between psychological determinants and sports engagement. A stratified random sampling technique was used to determine the number of participants. This study was used descriptive statistical tool of Mean, standard deviation and Pearson-r to interpret the data. The results revealed that psychological determinants are moderate with an overall mean of 2.94, while sports engagement is high with an overall mean of 3.75. This study revealed that there was no significant relationship between psychological determinants and sports engagement (r -value=-.07, p -value .13). Additionally, the researcher designed a sports development based on the results.

Keywords: *education, psychological determinants, sports engagement, sports development program, Philippines*

Introduction

Sport engagement, according to Hanifah (2022), is a relationship between individual and sport-related activities that is characterized by favorable cognition, attitudes, and emotions, fostering a sense of belongingness. This is a significant importance in promoting physical wellness, nurturing social connections, and enhancing overall quality of life. However, as noted by OECD, Philippines (2021), only 33.6% of students engage in sports activities, highlighting the barriers to student sports engagement, such as academic pressures and socio-economic factors.

In Levanger, Norway, Bergin and Ligestad (2023) found that student-athletes quit sports for four main reasons: societal stigma, loss of interest, competing priorities, and lack of time. They also noted that school schedules often make it difficult for athletes to stay committed. Similarly, In the United States, Shipherd et al. (2024), reported that student-athletes in the United States struggle to balance academics and sports, leading to burnout and eventual disengagement. Meanwhile, Pakistan, Gelen (2021) identified five factors that cause student-athletes to disengage: training demands, social life, health issues, mental stress, and academic pressures. These factors accumulate over time, making it difficult for athletes to balance their academic and athletic responsibilities, ultimately leading to dropout.

In Laguna, Philippines, Aquino and Reyes (2022) found that sports engagement among students-athletes in Laguna is closely tied to their sense of identity. However, external pressures, like the time demands of training and competition, can affect this engagement. The study also highlighted that support from coaches, teammates, and family is crucial for sustaining commitment, while lack of support can lead to disengagement or quitting. Further, In Pasay City, Metro Manila, Maghanoy (2023) found that students-athletes often lose their passion for sports and quit training due to burnout. They struggle to balance academic responsibilities with athletic training, manage family expectations, and deal with financial challenges. These issues stem from various sources, including physical, social, psychological, and financial pressures.

Fear and anxiety are emotional responses influenced by various psychological factors, particularly in high-stress environments like sports (Zhang, 2018). These emotions can significantly impact sports engagement, affecting athletes' vigor, absorption, and dedication. Understanding how fear and anxiety relate to psychological determinants is crucial for optimizing performance (Tamminen & Dunn, 2022).

With the aforementioned issues about psychological determinants of sports participation and their sport engagement, few studies have dealt with similar variables in Mindanao since they have the sufficient number of students who will be able to satisfy the criteria set in the selection of the research respondents especially in Cotabato Province. Moreover, the researcher failed to access studies dealing with the relationship of the combined variables, such as psychological determinants of sports participation and sports engagement of college students in the Cotabato Region. To mention a few, most of the published research like those done by Ohuruogu et al. (2022) revealed in their study that athletes at higher institutions in Ebonyi State in Nigeria that participation in sports is influenced by their fear of injury. This was supported by the study of Nummenmaa (2015) that fear is usually triggered by a circumstance that could be dangerous, that it is a natural defense response, and that it affects the sympathetic nervous system and fear is a negatively toned emotion that is usually experienced prior to performance and is strongly associated with the prevailing circumstance. Hence, it is due to the gaps mentioned above in the literature that the researcher felt the need to conduct a study dealing with psychological determinants of sports

participation and their sport engagement of college students in Cotabato Province. This study will shed light on the factors affecting student's engagement in the region. This study is limited to the Philippine context, specifically within Cotabato Province. However, there needs to be more research about the relationship between psychological determinants of sports participation and engagement in sports, much less here at Cotabato Province.

For this reason, this study primarily focuses on examining the psychological determinants of fear and anxiety in sports participation and engagement among students. While fear and anxiety are the central psychological factors addressed, it is important to note that other psychological determinants such as self-confidence, Intrinsic and Extrinsic motivation, also play significant roles in sports engagement. However, these factors are not the main focus of this study. The findings will specifically explore how fear and anxiety influence college students' involvement in sports, leaving the exploration of other psychological variables for future research. Understanding this context and the connection between psychological determinants and sports engagement is essential in creating enhanced holistic sports development program to enable students to maximize their athletic abilities and performance in a sporting environment.

The researcher wanted to share the findings of this study to the Institute of Sports, Physical Education, and Recreation (ISPEAR) of the University of Southern Mindanao through the governing body, including coaches, school administrators, teachers, and students, for further understanding of the importance of psychological determinants of sports participation in the engagement of the student-athletes in their chosen sports. With this, an enhanced program of more diverse sports opportunities will be presented by the researcher that consists of mentorship for development programs, workshops, and symposiums that address the increasing sports disengagement of students. Further, the findings of the study will be disseminated through research conferences, research forums, academic journals, public journals, and academic institutional libraries and to publish the study internationally for further dissemination of the result.

Research Questions

The study aimed to analyze the influence of psychological determinants of sports participation on college student's sports engagement. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of psychological determinants of sports participation among college students, in terms of:
 - 1.1. fear; and
 - 1.2. anxiety?
2. What is the level of sports engagement among college students in terms of:
 - 2.1. vigor;
 - 2.2. dedication; and
 - 2.3. absorption?
3. Is there a significant relationship between psychological determinants of sports participation and sports engagement of college students;
4. Based on the findings, what sports development program can be proposed for the improvement of sports engagement of college students?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. According to Creswell and Creswell (2017) describe quantitative research as a systematic method for exploring phenomena and relationships among variable through numerical data and statistical analysis. This method was selected for the study because it is a systematic process of gathering and analyzing data that makes it easier to research the variable and their intercorrelation. Through this technique, a researcher can measure and interpret the strength and direction of the relationship and, therefore, clearly and measurably explain the subject.

Additionally, this study used a descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research focuses to providing an in-depth and accurate description of the characteristics of a particular group, phenomenon or event. It will assist in the identification of some valuable information concerning participants' demographics, behaviors, and attributes, which become the foundation for further correlational analysis. According to Trochim and Donnelly (2008) correlational research investigates the relationships that exist between variables without changing them. This method permits the determination of relationships and to check whether changes in one explained that correlational research examines the relationships between variables without altering them. This method allows researchers to detect some relationships and establish whether one variable is change while, at the same time, a change in another variable also occurs without experimental control.

In this study, the quantitative descriptive-correlational research design was highly suitable for this study because it relates to the objective of exploring the relationship of psychological factors affecting sports participation and sports engagement among college students. Grounded in relevant literature, this design allows the systematic collection and in-depth analysis of quantitative data, providing meaningful insights into the research question.

Respondents

In this study, the respondents were 400 college students in public and private colleges and universities in Cotabato Province, mainly males and females, who enrolled in undergraduate programs for the academic year 2024-2025. Moreover, students outside Cotabato Province who were not enrolled in undergraduate programs for the academic year 2024-2025 were not included as respondents of this study. In addition, the respondents were chosen regardless of age, gender, courses, and sports events. This study utilized a stratified random sampling technique to choose its respondents. In this, the population is split into different subgroups or strata based on the ascribed characteristics and then sampling is done randomly from each group. Makwana et al. (2023) stated that stratified random sampling is used in most research studies to guarantee that the sample selected will represent the population and reduce variability within each subgroup, hence leading to more reliable results. In this study, the population was stratified according to School: School A, School B, and School C, and by year level: Freshmen, Sophomores, Junior, and Seniors. To minimize error, the researcher targeted 400 participants with a distribution of 33.33 percent of the sample set in the three schools sampled. Additionally, each of the School's samples comprised 25 percent from every year level so that both male and female students were equitably represented.

Moreover, by using the Raosoft sample size calculator, it was determined to have a sample size of 400. College students were selected as the respondents as they are the most relevant respondents to the objectives of the research. Their experiences and perspectives would be of paramount importance in bringing out valuable insights into the psychological factors influencing participation in sports and meaningful views about sports engagement.

Instrument

The researcher used and adapted a research tool to measure the psychological determinants of sports participation and sports engagement. The expert consultation was conducted for the survey questionnaire validation with a view to testing reliability. In this process, it was ensured that the items applied were relevant to the psychological determinants of sports participation and engagement among college students. In addition, this process aimed at ensuring the readability and intelligibility of the questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha coefficient at the result of reliability analysis of the study is 0.7. For evaluating the psychological determinants of sports participation, researcher has used the already validated tool by Ohuruogu et al. from their research work of (2022).

The first part of the survey questionnaire was taken from the study Psychological Determinants of Sports Participation among Athletes of Tertiary Institutions in Ebonyi State (Ohuruogu et al., 2022). This part has 14 items that are categorized into two: 8 items on fear and 6 items on anxiety. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for these factors was 0.8, which shows that it is highly reliable. Descriptive statistics were further applied to establish the distribution of responses, thus analyzing the psychological determinants affecting the college students.

Participants were asked to respond to each question on a 5-point Likert scale using the following values: 5 (very high), 4 (high), 3 (moderately high), 2 (low), and 1. (very low). The researcher used the range of margins, descriptions, and interpretations described below to interpret the psychological determinants of sports participation.

The second part of the survey questionnaire was adapted from The Sport Engagement Scale: An Adaptation of the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) for the Sports Environment (Guillen & Martinez-Alvarado., 2014). It is composed of 15 items distributed in three factors of five items each: Vigor (5 items), Dedication (5 items) and Absorption (5 items). The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the factors was found to be 0.9. Since the result was very good, the Cronbach's alpha value was interpreted as very good internal consistency. In evaluating the Sports engagement of students, a 5-point Likert scale will be used with the following values: 5 (very high), 4 (high), 3 (moderately high), 2 (low), and 1. (very low).

Procedure

In conducting this study, the researcher adhered to strict systematic procedures to encompass ethical considerations and minimize risks in the process. First, the researcher secured a letter of permission to gather data from the UIC Graduate School Dean. Then, the researcher submitted a letter to the UIC – Research Ethics Committee asking permission for the study's ethical clearance. When the researcher received the ethical clearance, she writes a letter to the school heads of the tertiary schools selected.

The respondents were requested to sign the informed consent form, which was specified in the instrument for voluntary participation in the study. The study only took into account individuals who signed the consent letter. The respondents were given the assurance that their answers would be kept private and that their names would not be included elsewhere in the study. The researcher ensured that the respondents' data and privacy were maintained confidentially. The rest will request and ask the respondents to answer in an entirely honest manner. The respondents were given time to complete the questionnaire correctly. The survey was done from June to November 2024.

The data gathered from the research instrument were tallied and computed for interpretation according to the frequency of times checked by the participants.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used to interpret the data to be collected.

Mean. This tool was used to describe the level of psychological determinants of sports participation in terms of fear and anxiety to report the extent of sports engagement among college students in terms of vigor, absorption, and dedication.

Standard Deviation. This was used to determine how spread out, how far, or how close the students' responses were in relation to the mean.

Pearson Product –Moment Correlation Coefficient. This statistical tool was used to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between psychological determinants of sports participation and sports engagement.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the overall level of psychological determinants of sports participation among college students. It shows an overall mean of 2.94, described as moderate. This means that psychological determinants of the students are sometimes evident. This implies that students believe that the fear and anxiety can affect their willingness to participate in sports. Fear is generally low, with students occasionally concerned about injury, they experience a high level of anxiety when participating in sports, particularly when they know they will be performing in front of spectators. This indicates that anxiety affects students' motivation and their willingness to participate in sports. In addition, the overall standard deviation was .43, which indicates that the respondent's ratings were less than one almost identical to one another.

Table 1. *Level of Psychological Determinants of Sports Participation among College Students*

	Mean	SD	Description
Fear			
1. preventing fear of injury from participating in sports	3.49	.90	High
2. preventing fear of injury holds me not to participate in any sports activity	2.99	1.03	Moderate
3. preventing fear of injury from concentrating in sports activities.	3.03	1.01	Moderate
4. inducing fear among athletes by incurring injury during the game	2.53	.79	Moderate
5. discouraging colleagues from participating in athletic activities by incurring injury	2.71	.93	Moderate
6. preventing participation in athletic activities by associating every sport with the risk of injury, but this should not be allowed	1.91	.80	Low
7. taking care of injuries that occur during sports activities by the first aid team	1.57	.68	Very Low
8. limiting good athletes from performing at their best due to fear of injury	2.03	.89	Low
Category Mean	2.49	.53	Low
Anxiety			
9. feeling nervous about performing before spectators	3.69	.88	High
10. getting easily teased up by competitors' taunts during the game	3.06	.96	Moderate
11. being easily overtaken by stress	3.29	1.02	Moderate
12. feeling anxious almost all the time about something or someone	3.32	1.01	Moderate
13. feeling like I am a failure sometimes	3.55	1.02	High
14. losing focus during the game due to negative comments from my teammates, as I am a very sensitive person	3.40	1.17	High
Category Mean	3.41	.76	High
Over-all Mean	2.94	.43	Moderate

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Very High; 3.40-4.19, High; 2.60-3.39, Moderate; 1.80-2.59, Low; 1.00-1.79, Very Low

The findings align with the study by Prapavessis et al. (2015), which highlighted that moderate levels of psychological factors are common among athletes, particularly in competitive settings. The authors observe that if well managed, pre-competition anxiety can improve attention and preparation but will negatively impact performance if not addressed. The study highlights cognitive anxiety, particularly the fear of failure, as a critical factor influencing athletes' mental states. This is in line with Smith et al. (2019), who reported that students indicated moderate levels of psychological factors that sharpened focus on technique, risk assessment, and decision-making, which reduced the risk of injury are more likely to take deliberate steps to avoid risky behavior or overexertion, thus reducing their injury risk during training or competition. This also agrees with Pal et al (2021), which observed that moderate anxiety due to the fear of injury motivates athletes to comply with the safety measures and guidelines provided for enhancing wellness and performance.

Fear. It is revealed that the category mean is 2.49, described as low, with the mean rating of the items ranging from 1.57 to 3.49. Consequently, the item, taking care of injuries that occur during sports activities by the first aid team, has a mean of 1.57, while the item, preventing fear of injury from participating in sports, has a mean rating of 3.49. This suggests that students place larger emphasis on addressing the fear of injury, which affects their willingness to participate in sports. When students feel confident about their safety, they are more likely to engage in sports without being hindered by fears of injury, permitting them to focus on enjoying the activity.

Further, this finding further supports the conclusion by Ford et al. (2017), who indicated that athletes who fear of injuries less more likely to perform optimally in high-stakes situations, as they were held back by anxiety or hesitation restrained them. Their study found that athletes perform at the optimal level when they have maintained a balanced level of fear that is enough to make them aware of possible danger but not so high as to interfere with their actions. Low levels of fear allow athletes to take risks intended and participate

in their actions without undue hesitation. Moreover, this study fits with the research of Mills et al. (2018), who investigated the relationship between low fear of injury and improved motor skills performance in interaction sports such as rugby and soccer. Their finding suggest that low fear enables athletes to execute their movements more effectively, leading to better inclusive performance.

Anxiety. It is revealed that its category mean is 3.41, described as high, with mean ratings ranging from 3.06 to 3.69. Consequently, the item, getting easily teased up by competitors' taunts during the game, has a mean of 3.06 while the item, feeling nervous about performing before spectators, has a mean rating of 3.69. This implies that students experience a high level of anxiety when participating in sports, particularly when they know they will be performing in front of spectators. They feel nervous and pressured to perform well, whether in front of peers, teachers, or parents, and fear of making mistakes, being judged, or failing to meet the expectations of others.

This finding supports the argument of Jones M. and Hanton S. (2017) which revealed that anxiety levels were higher in athletes who performed in front of an audience compared to those who did not. This work further supports the idea that the presence of spectators increases anxiety levels, which can affect an athlete's ability to perform well. Moreover, in the study of Cox (2021), he discusses how heightened anxiety can lead to performance decrements, especially when the athlete is highly focused on others' perceptions. Additionally, In the study of McNally (2003), he mentioned that high anxiety levels can lead to emotional distress, including increased irritability, worry, and an increased risk of developing mood disorders like depression.

Level of Sports Engagement among College Students

Table 2 presents the level of sports engagement among college students with an overall mean rating of 3.75 described as high, which means that sports engagement of the student is oftentimes observed. It implies that college students exhibit a high level of sports engagement, driven by psychological factors such as vigor, dedication, and absorption. These psychological factors increased the students' level of engagement in sports. The overall standard deviation is .64, which indicates that the respondent's ratings were less than one almost identical to one another.

Table 2. *Level of Sports Engagement among College Students*

	Mean	SD	Description
Vigor			
1. attending trainings is an option for me	3.66	1.00	High
2. being persistent in activity is one of my strengths	3.64	1.00	High
3. having energy during my training ang matches is essential	3.80	.90	High
4. looking forward to going to training is a daily habit of mine	3.21	.99	Moderate
5. being strong and vigorous in my sport activity is a goal strive for.	3.46	.95	High
Category Mean	3.55	.83	High
Dedication			
6. setting a self-challenge in my sport activity drives me forward	3.93	.83	High
7. being enthusiastic about my sport activity is what motivates me forward	3.76	.90	High
8. being proud of the work I do in my sport activity gives me a sense of accomplishment	4.20	.81	Very High
9. having a sport activity that is full of meaning and resolve gives me direction	4.02	.87	High
10. feeling inspired while carrying out my sport activity is what keeps me going	3.98	.87	High
Category Mean	3.99	.76	High
Absorption			
11. being carried away by my sport activity is a natural feeling for me	3.58	.94	High
12. feeling happy when I am engrossed in my sport activity is a reward in itself	3.99	.86	High
13. being oblivious to everything around me when I'm training or competing allows me to focus	3.64	.91	High
14. being absorbed in my sport activity is what I love about it	3.61	.86	High
15. time flying when I'm training or competing is a sign of how much I enjoy it	3.80	.93	High
Category Mean	3.72	.69	High
Over-all Mean	3.75	.64	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Very High; 3.40-4.19, High; 2.60-3.39, Moderate; 1.80-2.59, Low; 1.00-1.79, Very Low

This finding aligns with the study of Martins et al. (2019), who found that students with high sports engagement are driven by intrinsic goals like personal growth and skill mastery, which motivate continuous improvement. Furthermore, this result aligns with the study of Kukoda (2022) who emphasized the connection between athletic engagement and the perception of success, noting that students who are highly dedicated to sports participation are more likely to have a heightened sense of success due to the stronger emotional and cognitive engagement they experience. Additionally, this aligns with Ozkara et al. (2016) who found that athletes with high vigor sustain better performance and show greater psychological resilience, reducing the risk of burnout.

Vigor. Its category mean is 3.55, described as high, with mean ratings ranging from 3.21 to 3.66. Notably, the item, looking forward to going to training, is a daily habit of mine and has a mean of 3.21, while the item, attending training, is an option for me and has a mean rating of 3.66. This implies that students are highly motivated and energized, as training sessions have become a daily habit for them. They develop a sense of responsibility toward their sport and a desire to perform well, which drives their commitment and willingness to participate actively. Regular training enhances their physical abilities and boosts their confidence, making them more

eager to engage in practice and competitions.

In support, the findings were consistent with the information provided by Lonsdale (2016), who defined vigor as a core dimension of sports engagement. High vigor was described as an athlete's ability to maintain high energy levels and enthusiasm for training and competition. Their research found that athletes with high vigor were more likely to persist in demanding activities and achieve better performance outcomes. Moreover, the result aligns with Clancy et al. (2016) that athletes with greater mental toughness also reported higher vigor, allowing them to maintain focus and energy during high-pressure situations, such as competitions or intensive training sessions.

Dedication. As assessed by the respondents, it has a high category mean of 3.99 with mean ratings of 3.76 to 4.20. On the one hand, the item being enthusiastic about my sports activity is what motivates me forward and reflects a mean rating of 3.76. On the other hand, the item of being proud of the work I do in my sports activity gives me a sense of accomplishment. I got a mean rating of 4.20, which is very high. This suggests that students are driven in their sports activities, as they experience confident emotions such as interest, motivation, and pride in their accomplishments. When students feel a sense of pride and personal accomplishment from their performance, it strengthens their connection to the sport and inspires continued participation. Additionally, the high overall mean rating suggests that the more students feel proud of their accomplishments and personal fulfillment in their sports activities, the higher their engagement rate remains.

Further, this study supports the view of Lonsdale (2016), who initiate that athletes with high dedication are characterized by their willingness to persist in rigorous training and overcome setbacks. The study revealed that dedication is strongly linked to intrinsic motivation, as dedicated athletes often report finding meaning and enjoyment in their sport. Moreover, this result is similar to that of Hodge et al. (2017). High dedication emerged as a critical component of long-term success. Athletes with high dedication reported a deep sense of purpose and passion for their sport, which helped them maintain high levels of performance and overcome obstacles such as injuries or competitive stress.

Absorption. It has garnered a high category mean rating of 3.72, with a mean rating that ranges from 3.61 to 3.99. Notably, the item being absorbed in my sports activity is what I love about it, reflecting a mean rating of 3.61. Meanwhile, the item, feeling happy when I am engrossed in my sports activity, is a reward in itself, showing a mean rating of 3.99. It suggests that college students particularly enjoy the sense of happiness from being engrossed in their sports activities. This sense of fulfillment encourages continued participation and boosts their overall well-being, creating a positive feedback loop where the enjoyment they feel increases their desire to engage in sports regularly.

This finding supports the study by Liu et al. (2022) that students with high absorption in sports were more likely to perform at higher levels during competitions. Their intense focus led to better coordination, faster decision-making, and more effective execution of skills. Additionally, this aligns with Lev and Levental (2024) work, which revealed that high absorption levels often lead to flow, where athletes are completely immersed in their performance. This results in improved focus, enjoyment, and optimal performance.

Significance of the Relationship of Psychological Determinants of Sports Participation and Sports Engagement of the College Students

Shown in Table 3 is the relationship between psychological determinants of sports participation and sports engagement of college students. It shows that psychological determinants of sports participation have a weak negative relationship of sports engagement with ($r = -.07$). It also reflects a p -value of .13, which was greater than the level of significance set at .05 two-tailed. This implies that there is no significant relationship between psychological factors, and it does not provide sufficient evidence to suggest that these factors alone influence sports engagement or participation.

Table 3. *Significance of the Relationship of Psychological Determinants of Sports Participation and Sports Engagement of the College Students*

	Sports Engagement		
	r	p -value	Remarks
Psychological Determinants of Sports Participation	-.07	.13	Not Significant

***Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

These findings are consistent with the study by Zhang et al. (2018), which explored how psychological factors such as fear and anxiety affect sports participation and engagement. The authors found that psychological determinants sometimes have weak or insignificant relationships with engagement, particularly when personal or environmental stressors diminish an athlete's enjoyment and satisfaction. This claim aligns with Simbula and Guglielmi (2018) study, which examined the psychological barriers to sports engagement among students, focusing on fear of failure and anxiety. Their results showed that fear and anxiety were present among participants but these emotional factors did not significantly correlate with engagement in sports. They concluded that situational factors, such as time availability and social support, played a stronger role in determining sports participation. Additionally, this result also supports Guglielmi et al. (2019) research, who found that there is no significant relationship between anxiety and sports engagement. Although anxiety was present among athletes but it did not seem to affect their overall engagement in sports.

Finally, the results of the study supported the theory of Kearsley and Shneiderman (1998) idea of Engagement Theory which holds

students to connect with learning activities through interaction with others and through meaningful activity tasks. It analyzed in their study on how psychological determinants and other factors affects the engagement of students in sports (York et al., 2015). Furthermore, when students receive less support from family and friends, they tend to have lower motivation to win their chosen sports. Funds and monetary support are part of the structural support of students; the disengagement sports of the athlete may cause a lack of sports equipment, allowances, and registration in events that constrain them from playing (Ommundsen & Vaglum, 1997).

Sports Development Program

This proposed program will be based on the psychological determinants that center on preparing students with the tools and plans that will ultimately make for success on and off the field. In addressing anxiety and fear, the purposes of the program are to help students develop effective coping mechanisms to manage high-pressure situations. Increasing strength and uptake will ensure students maintain energy levels, focus, and full immersion during training and competitions. Cultivating commitment will provide long-term devotion to the sport even under adverse circumstances. Students will be able to achieve much more in their athletic pursuit and individual development by engaging in this approach.

This program contributes mental skills training, physical conditioning, and psychological support that ensures student development under a holistic approach. There is improved performance, resilience build, increased mental toughness, and the feeling of emotional attachment to the sport after designing certain activities and making suitable strategy adjustments. The point of focus will be creating stability in achieving an athletic career with long-term sustainability by optimizing performance potential in any sports discipline or area of life. The program's main goals are to develop into fine all-around persons on the field and off. All of these will be achieved with much emphasis on physical growth alongside psychological development.

Conclusions

Considering the results of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The college students in Cotabato Province exhibited a moderate level of psychological determinants of sports participation. This suggests that psychological barriers, such as fear and anxiety, were sometimes evident and hindered students from actively engaging in sports. Addressing these psychological factors is crucial in fostering a supportive environment that encourages greater participation. Additionally, the students demonstrated a high level of sports engagement, characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption, indicating that their motivation and focus on sports often led to positive emotional and psychological benefits. However, the study found no significant relationship between psychological determinants of sports participation and sports engagement, suggesting that these factors insignificantly affect sports involvement. Lastly, a holistic sports development program was proposed to address both physical and psychological barriers, focusing on improving mental and emotional wellness to promote a more inclusive sports culture.

Based on the study's conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

Given the moderate level of psychological determinants, particularly fear and anxiety, it is recommended that PE teachers and sports coordinators develop and implement intervention programs to help students manage these barriers. These programs should involve collaboration with mental health professionals and include workshops on stress management, mindfulness, and coping skills for performance anxiety. Regular assessments should be conducted to monitor students' psychological well-being and adjust interventions as necessary.

To elevate the high level of sports engagement to a very high level, PE teachers and sports coordinators should continue promoting an environment that fosters vigor, dedication, and absorption. This can be achieved by setting achievable goals, offering a variety of sports activities, and providing positive reinforcement. Encouraging students to monitor their progress and adopt a growth-oriented mindset will enhance their motivation, confidence, and enjoyment.

Since the study found no significant relationship between psychological determinants and sports engagement, external factors such as social support and personal interests may have a greater influence on participation. Future researchers should explore these factors, including peer interactions and personal preferences, to better understand their impact. Universities should promote peer-driven sports activities and offer options aligned with students' interests to enhance engagement.

To address both psychological and physical barriers, future researchers are encouraged to introduce and utilize the crafted holistic sports development program. This program should focus on improving mental, emotional, and physical well-being by providing support to overcome anxiety and fear. Regular evaluations should be conducted to assess the program's effectiveness and make necessary adjustments. Collaboration with mental health professionals and physical trainers will be essential in creating a comprehensive program that enhances sports participation and overall student well-being.

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